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Paid internship: legal foundations, social significance and current issues

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Introduction

One of the priorities of state policy towards young people in our country is to prepare them for the labor market, develop professional skills and improve their qualifications through practice. In particular, internships for students studying in higher education institutions play an important role in combining their theoretical knowledge with practice.

The institution of "paid internship", which has become widespread in world practice in recent years, is being gradually introduced in Uzbekistan. In this case, the intern (student) receives a salary for his practical work on a legal basis, which serves to ensure the principles of social justice and protect the labor rights of young people.

This article discusses the legal foundations of the concept of paid internship, its economic and social significance, and current problems in Uzbekistan.

Main part

1. The concept and legal basis of paid internships

An intern (Latin: stagiarius - practitioner) is a graduate or student of a professional or higher education institution who temporarily works in a particular enterprise or organization in order to gain practical knowledge and skills. Typically, their work is temporary during the internship period.

A paid internship is a temporary form of employment in which the intern receives a monetary reward or salary for a certain amount of work within the framework of his/her work activity. This institution is regulated in many countries under labor law and education legislation.

The legal framework for internships in the Republic of Uzbekistan is established by the Labor Code, the Law "On Education", as well as relevant resolutions of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education. Article 34 of **the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the new edition, adopted on April 30, 2022** (entered into force on April 1, 2023), stipulates that a person with whom an employment contract has been concluded must be paid for his labor.

No. PQ-190 of April 13, 2022, also strengthens mechanisms for employing young people through paid internships.

Although the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide a direct legal definition of the concept of an intern, in some cases, persons undergoing internships are recognized as employees. Article 17 of the new Labor Code defines the parties to labor relations and provides that labor rights arise in the event of an employment contract between the employer and the employee.

2. Social and economic importance

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The introduction of paid internships provides the following positive aspects:

- **It strengthens the financial independence of young people.** The student earns income while applying his knowledge in practice.
- **Professional skills are developed,** which ensures the training of personnel that meet market requirements.
- **Benefits for employers:** Through an intern, the employer will have the opportunity to select personnel.
- **Social equality is ensured.** Equal opportunities are created for children from low-income families.

In international experience, paid internships in countries such as Germany, the USA, and France are carried out with full consideration of students' labor rights. In the USA, interns are entitled to wages and other rights based on the Fair Labor Standards Act (US Department of Labor, 2021).

3. Current issues and proposals

There are several problems with the implementation of a paid internship system:

Regulatory and legal gaps. In some cases, internships are carried out on a "volunteering" basis, rather than on the basis of an employment contract, which leaves interns without legal protection.

The legal status of interns is determined by the following factors:

Interns working under an employment contract have the status of full-fledged employees and are entitled to all rights and guarantees established by the Labor Code: working hours, rest, remuneration, labor protection, social insurance, etc.

Interns who are only undergoing internships without concluding an employment contract - they are usually sent for internships on the basis of cooperation between an educational institution and an organization. Such interns are not considered subjects of labor law, but rather participants in the educational process.

This distinction makes their legal status unclear, especially in cases of accidents during production practice, which raises issues of legal liability. Therefore, it is necessary to regulate the activities of interns on the basis of a clear legal status.

Employer passivity. Many private businesses avoid the obligation to pay.

Limited financial resources. The financial mechanism between educational institutions and employers is not fully functioning.

Suggestions:

1. Introduction of a separate article to the Labor Code defining the concept of an intern and their status;
2. Introduction of a tripartite agreement between higher education institutions, interns, and employers;
3. Development of a regulatory document establishing minimum guarantees for interns (rest, labor protection, compensation);
4. Legally regulate the employer's liability for accidents that occur during internships.

Conclusion

Paid internships play a major role not only in the professional growth of young people, but also in their legal, financial and social independence. A clear legal definition of the status of interns

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within the framework of labor law is important not only to protect their rights, but also to ensure the effectiveness of the state's youth policy. The imperfection of the regulatory framework not only weakens the legal status of interns, but also complicates relations between employers and educational institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to modernize labor legislation and develop the institution of internships on a legal basis, taking into account international experience. For the effective implementation of this institution, it is necessary to harmonize labor and education legislation, eliminate legal gaps and increase the responsibility of employers. This will serve long-term social stability and economic development.

References

1. Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (new edition), April 30, 2022.
2. Law "On Education", 2020.
3. Presidential Decree No. PQ-190, April 13, 2022.
4. US Department of Labor. (2021). *Fact Sheet #71: Internship Programs Under The Fair Labor Standards Act* .
5. European Commission. (2020). *Quality Framework for Traineeships* .
6. lex.uz – National database of legislative documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.